

A high-quality reference genome assembly for the devil firefish, *Pterois miles*

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ABSTRACT

Exploring the genetic background of successful invasive phenotypes is essential in understanding their underlying mechanisms. Lionfish (Scorpaenidae) are identified among the most prosperous invaders spread along the coastlines of the Atlantic and recently the Mediterranean Sea. However, within this family, the genomic resources are depauperate while reference genome assemblies are totally absent. In this study, we focus on the devil firefish, *Pterois miles* (Bennett, 1828), one of the most successful invasive species across the coasts of the Mediterranean Sea. We sequenced the genome of *P. miles* using Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) and Illumina reads for building the reference genome. The resulting assembly consisted of 660 contigs and scaffolds (N50 = 14,5 Mb) with a total size of about 902 Mb, while delivering 98% BUSCO completeness. The high-quality *de novo* genome assembly constructed here is the first one among the members of Scorpaenidae and establishes the outset for further exploring this family and the biology of venomous and invasive species.

BACKGROUND

The devil firefish, *Pterois miles* (Bennett, 1828), is a venomous species native to the Indo-Pacific region, from South Africa to Red Sea and East to Sumatra (Shultz, 1986, FishBase) and belongs to the Scorpaenidae family. The first occurrence of *P. miles*, as a single specimen, in the Mediterranean Sea has been recorded by the Levantine coast in 1991

(Golani and Sonin, 1992), while the second, of two individuals, was almost twenty years later (Bariche et al., 2013). Soon after, the frequency of appearances, along the Mediterranean, rapidly increased (Crocetta et al., 2015; Dailianis et al. 2016; Kleitou et al., 2016; Bilge et al., 2017; Giovos et al., 2018; Al Mabruk and Rizgalla, 2019; Katsanevakis et al., 2020; Vavasis et al., 2020). While the origin of species colonization in the Mediterranean Sea follows the invasion pattern of other Lessepsian immigrants introduced from the Red Sea, through Suez Canal (Bariche et al., 2013; Kleitou et al., 2016; Bariche et al., 2017; Chiesa et al., 2019; Dimitriou et al., 2019), the possible contribution of long-distance dispersal via aquarium trading cannot be ruled out (Bariche et al., 2017; Dimitriou et al., 2019).

Lionfish (genus: *Pterois*) are considered among the most thriving invaders in the history of marine invasions (Albins and Hixon 2008) because of their rapid expansion worldwide (Azzurro et al., 2017). Indeed, the introduction of *P. miles* and a con-generic species *P. volitans*, together referred as the invasive lionfish complex (Lyons et al., 2019), in the western Atlantic is one of the fastest and most ecologically harmful marine fish introductions to date (Kleitou et al., 2016 and references therein). Invasive non-indigenous marine species, in general, are considered to have a major impact on local biodiversity while threatening marine industries and frequently human health (Bax et al., 2003; Arim et al., 2005; Blakeslee et al., 2019). Data derived from Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) could provide promising opportunities in the exploration of potential adaptations that shape invasive fitness.

Factors associated with *P. miles* biology such as the signature antipredatory defenses, discernible predatory behaviour, low parasitism and ecological flexibility probably explain its rapid diaspora in the Mediterranean (Dailianis et al., 2016), whereas the dynamics of species' populations indicate a rapidly progressing increase along the coastlines (Kleitou et al., 2016). Yet, genomic references of species are missing, while only mitochondrial genome (Dray et al., 2016) and DNA barcoding data (Chiesa et al., 2019 and references therein) are available so far.

Here, we report the first high-quality genome assembly of *P. miles* constructed through a combination of Illumina with ONT reads. This valuable resource, the first representative genome within the family of Scorpaenidae, will be critical for unveiling the genetic background of the species' biology, ecology and evolution especially in relation to the invasive traits.

METHODS

1. Sample collection, libraries construction & sequencing

Animal care and handling were carried out following well established guidelines (Degrazia and Beauchamp, 2019).

A specimen was caught alive in Bali (North coast), Crete, Greece and was transferred in the indoor facilities of Cretaquarium, an aquarium which is part of the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR). The specimen was kept alive for three weeks in a 150 L tank with semi-closed circuit with airlift, mechanical and biological filtration, water recirculation rates of 30 and 100%/h. Temperature was adjusted at 19 °C +/- 1,0 °C and the photoperiod was set to 12hL:12hD. The specimen was anesthetized using clove oil, and blood was collected with a sterilized and heparinized syringe from the caudal vein of the fish. Blood was kept in sterilized and heparinized 1.5 ml tubes on ice, until DNA extraction.

DNA was extracted, for the purpose of ONT sequencing, from blood with the Qiagen Genomic Tip 100/G kit. Three ligation libraries (SQK-LSK109) were constructed using 2.3 microgram DNA as input for each library. The libraries were sequenced on two R9.4.1 flow cells, on a MinION Mk1B and a MinION Mk1C sequencer, respectively. The resulting fast5-files were basecalled with Guppy v5.0.11, using the 'sup' (super-accuracy) configuration and a minimum quality score of 7.

For the Illumina sequencing, the same procedure and protocol were used. 4 µl of blood were eluted in 100 µl AE buffer which resulted in 79,2 ng/µl (Qubit measurement) of extra pure DNA ($260/280 = 1,85$ & $260/230 = 2,21$). DNA integrity was assessed by electrophoresis in 0.4 % w/v megabase agarose gel. The template DNA for Illumina sequencing was sheared by ultrasonication in a Covaris instrument. A PCR-free library was prepared with the Kapa Hyper Prep DNA kit with TruSeq Unique Dual Indexing.

The sequencing was performed on an Illumina Hiseq4000 platform by the Norwegian Sequencing Centre (www.sequencing.uio.no), a national technology platform hosted by the University of Oslo.

2. Data pre-processing

The length filtering and adapter trimming of basecalled ONT reads were carried out with Porechop v0.2.4 (<https://github.com/rrwick/Porechop>) using default parameters, adding the

extra flag of “--discard_middle” to prune reads with possible inner adapters. The quality control was performed using Nanoplot v.1.20 (De Coster et al., 2018).

The quality assessment of raw Illumina reads was performed with FastQC v0.11.9 (Andrews, 2017) while the filtering of low quality reads and adapter trimming with Trimmomatic v0.39 (Bolger et al., 2014). The reads were processed with the following parameters: (i) 4-based sliding window with cutting threshold score lower than 15 Phred (SLIDINGWINDOW: 4:15), (ii) leading and trailing bases with score less than 10 are pruned (LEADING: 10, TRAILING: 10), (iii) reads shorter than 75 bp and average score lower than 30 Phred are removed (MINLEN: 75, AVGQUAL: 30).

3. De novo genome assembly

For the *de novo* assembly, using a hybrid approach, we combined long reads from ONT with short and accurate Illumina reads. The ONT reads were used for the construction of the initial *de novo* assembly, while the Illumina reads were used for the polishing procedure afterwards. To build the draft assembly from the ONT reads we used Flye v2.9. (Kolmogorov et al., 2019), which uses a repeat graph as core data structure, with default parameters and a genome size estimation of 900Mb. The draft assembly was polished in two rounds with RACON v1.4.3 (Vaser et al., 2017) using the filtered long reads, mapped against the draft assembly by Minimap v2.22 (Li, 2018). Further polishing of the assembly was performed with Medaka v1.4.4 (<https://github.com/nanoporetech/medaka>) and consequently with Pilon v1.23 (Walker et al., 2014) for which we used the preprocessed Illumina reads, previously mapped by Minimap v2.22 against the resulting assembly from Medaka.

The whole genome assembly pipeline which was used in the present study is containerized by Angelova et al (2022) (<https://github.com/genomenerds/SnakeCube>) and run in the IMBBC High-performance computing (HPC) facility “zorba” (Zafeiropoulos et al., 2021).

4. Quality assessment of draft assemblies

The resultant draft assemblies all through the procedure were evaluated by two commonly used criteria: (i) the N50 statistic from contigs’ size, using QUAST v.5.0.2 (Gurevich et al., 2013) and (ii) the completeness score based on the presence of universal single copy ortholog genes, using BUSCO v.5.2.2 (Manni et al., 2021) against Actinopterygii ortholog dataset 10 (actinopterygii_odb10). BUSCO was run with default parameters adding the extra flag of

“--augustus” to enable species-specific training for gene prediction by AUGUSTUS v.3.4 (<https://github.com/Gaius-Augustus/Augustus>).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sequencing yielded 38.66 Gb of raw ONT reads, from which 36.16 Gb were with quality above Q7, as well as 3.75 Gb of raw Illumina reads. After the pre-processing step of trimming and quality filtering, 35.72 Gb of ONT and 3.16 Gb of Illumina reads were kept (Table 1). The final genome assembly is constituted of 660 contigs with a total length of about 902 Mb. The longest contig is 36.4 Mb and N50 statistic of about 14.5 Mb (Table 2). Concerning genome completeness, 3566 genes out of 3640 have been found (98%), of the ones included in the BUSCO Actinopterygian ortholog dataset (v.10). By those, 3551 genes (97.6%) were identified as complete, while only 74 (2%) as missing (Table 2), suggesting a high level of contiguity and completeness of the aforementioned *de novo* genome assembly.

CONCLUSION

Here, we present the first reference-level genome of one of the most successful invaders around the world, devil firefish (*Pterois miles*). Devil firefish’s genome assembly of such quality will baseline the territory for future comparative studies, research of biology in the still unexplored family of Scorpaenidae and shed light on the unique traits of such successful invasions.

Table 1. Summary of sequencing throughput

Sequencing technology	Raw reads	Quality-controlled reads	Coverage
Illumina	24,836,074	20,980,358	3.5 x
MinION	2,245,868	2,224,738	39.5 x

Table 2. Polished genome assembly statistics and completeness

Number of contigs	660
Total length	902,353,306
GC (%)	40.78
Largest contig	36,477,432
N50	14,490,642
N75	5,565,202
BUSCO completeness score	
Complete	97.6%
Single	96.6%
Duplicated	1.0%
Fragmented	0.4%,
Missing	2.0%
Total number of orthologs (Actinopterygii)	3,640

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was supported through computational resources provided by IMBBC (Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture) of the HCMR (Hellenic Centre for Marine Research). Funding for establishing the IMBBC HPC has been received by the MARBIGEN (EU Regpot) project, LifeWatchGreece RI, and the CMBR (Centre for the study and sustainable exploitation of Marine Biological Resources) RI.

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